

New data on the stratigraphy of the Middle Jurassic siliciclastic rocks from the West Balkan Mountains (West Bulgaria)

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Abstract. The present study is a contribution to the lithostratigraphy of Middle Jurassic strata in the area of the Zimevitsa Plateau (West Balkan Mts, West Bulgaria). Based on its lithological and regional properties, the Dobravitsa Member is distinguished from the surrounding rocks of the Etropole Formation. The new member consists of alternating shales, siltstones and fine-grained sandstones. It also contains abundant siderite and calcite concretions, which are distributed in discrete stratigraphic horizons in both the mudrocks and coarser lithologies. Fossils are extremely rare. Poorly preserved ammonites and belemnites are found only. Based on several ammonite finds, the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation is assigned to a narrow stratigraphic interval of the lower Bajocian (unlimited, probably lower part of the *Witchellia laeviuscula* Zone). Although it has restricted lateral distribution, which is exclusively confined to its type-area, the Dobravitsa Member has a proper place in the formal Bulgarian Jurassic lithostratigraphic scheme, as it represents a discernible atypical development of the Etropole Formation in the West Balkan Mts region. Another emphasis of this study is laid on concretions from the Etropole Formation. Besides siderite and calcite concretions, a few examples of iron oxyhydroxide concretions, from localities outside the Zimevitsa Plateau area, are also described. The latter are also an atypical component of the Etropole Formation, which deserves a further special study and systematization, as it implies unknown history of this lithofacies, in both depositional and diagenetic terms.

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INTRODUCTION

The Middle Jurassic successions in Bulgaria comprise widespread continental-shelf sediments that often contain organic-rich strata. The latter occur in siliciclastic rocks (several tens of meters thick), which are currently exposed in the Western and

Central Balkan Mts Range (Balkan and Srednogie zones *sensu* Dabovski *et al.*, 2002), but mainly have broad subcrop occurrence in Moesia, North Bulgaria (Moesian Platform, *ibid.*). Amongst them, the Aalenian–Bajocian shale-siltstone-sandstone deposits of the Etropole Formation have a key regional significance (Sapunov, 1969; Sapunov and

Tchoumatchenco, 1986, 1989, 1991; Sapunov *et al.*, 1988, 1991; Juranov *et al.*, 1993; Sapunov and Metodiev, 2007). These rocks (divided into several formal members) grade vertically from older siliciclastic sediments but also sharply overlies shallow-marine carbonate strata of the Ozirvo Formation (Sapunov *et al.*, 1994, 1996, 1999). They are covered, with more or less abrupt lithologic contacts, by marl-shale-mudstone alternations of the Bov Formation, or shallow-water terrigenous-carbonate rocks of the Polaten Formation. It is known that the range of distribution of the Etropole Formation is framed laterally by the occurrence of coeval shallow-water strata (Sapunov *et al.*, 1985a). It is also known that, in the subsurface Jurassic successions of northeast Bulgaria, the Etropole Formation laterally grades into the Esenitsa Formation (Sapunov *et al.*, 1985b; 1986a, b). The onset of deposition of the Etropole Formation has a remarkable synchronicity, which is biostratigraphically well dated in many localities as concurrent with the Aalenian/Bajocian Stage boundary interval (Juranov *et al.*, 1993). The end of this expanded siliciclastic deposition is also well known stratigraphically and is approximately coincident with the lower/upper Bajocian Substage boundary (*ibid.*).

The Etropole Formation is known to be either homogeneous (almost entirely composed of clay- to silt-sized siliciclastic sediments) or more or less variegated (comprising larger lithological bodies or discrete beds/packages of coarse silt- to sand-sized siliciclastic rocks). Accordingly, in the homogeneous strata, it is represented by non-calcareous to slightly calcareous silty shales, whereas in the heterogeneous successions it is divided into the Nefela, Shipkovo, Lopyan and Stefanets members (see Sapunov and Tchoumatchenco, 1986, 1989, 1991; Juranov *et al.*, 1993). The former two members correspond to argillaceous siltstones that are unevenly distributed across the eastern part of the Western Fore-Balkan and Central Balkan Mts and span the lower Bajocian to the upper Bajocian (*pars.*) and the uppermost lower Bajocian, respectively (Juranov *et al.*, 1993). The Lopyan Member comprises a thick body of siltstones and subordinate sandstones that have both subcrop and outcrop distribution in central north Bulgaria, being of earliest Bajocian to late Bajocian age (*ibid.*). The Stefanets Member is an extensive lithological body of shales, which grades with short lithologic transitions into other members of the Etropole Formation and has Aalenian–early Bajocian age. The lithologies composing the heterogeneous Etropole Formation have highly variable thicknesses and diachronous intraformational

boundaries (*ibid.*). Regardless of whether the rocks of the Etropole Formation are undivided or subdivided, they commonly contain iron-bearing concretions and less commonly clayey-phosphorite and pyrite concretions, as well as locally developed argillaceous ironstones, the latter being usually positioned at the very base of the successions (*e.g.*, Nachev, 1976, 1988; Stoilov *et al.*, 2007).

Based on previous publications, it should be noted that the stratigraphy of the Etropole Formation is well established, but more facts can also be added. In the last few field seasons, it has been found that, in a limited area of the Western Balkan Mts where the Etropole Formation has always been considered homogeneous (*e.g.*, Haydutov *et al.*, 1995a, b), the sediments of this unit show particular intraformational lithological properties that allow for lithostratigraphic subdivision. A similar property from this area was also noticed during the latest geological mapping in scale 1:50 000 (Petrov, 2008), but it was briefly referred to and without going into detail. Following the rules and recommendations of the Stratigraphic Code of Bulgaria (Nikolov and Sapunov, 2002), this study establishes a new member of the Etropole Formation. The succession constituting the new member requires special attention from a depositional viewpoint, but more data will be given elsewhere.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The Jurassic sediments of the Western Balkan Mts have long been known for their good exposures and varied lithologies. This particularly applies to the outcrops of the Godech–Svoje area, which have attracted much attention from both the pioneers of the Jurassic geology and later workers (*e.g.*, Toula, 1893; Zlatarski, 1908; Atanasov, 1953; Nachev, 1976; Sapunov and Ziegler, 1976). Recently, the geology of the area, and in particular the presence of well-exposed sedimentary successions of various depositional settings, has been discussed from a conservational perspective, with a view towards the formal distinction of newly protected geological sites of high esthetic and scientific value (Valchev and Nachev, 2015). Regionally, this area is part of a continuous Mesozoic succession and is considered an integral part of the Balkan and Srednogie zones (*sensu* Dabovski *et al.*, 2002). The latter tectonic units are first-order structures of the Balkan orogenic system in Bulgaria (*ibid.*) (see Fig. 1a, b). Locally, the Jurassic strata of the Godech–Svoje area compose several uplands located between the

Fig. 1. Location maps: *a*) tectonic sketch-map of Bulgaria showing the study area (after Dabovski *et al.*, 2002); *b*) simplified map showing the distribution of Jurassic rocks in the Balkan and Srednogorie zones (Godech–Svoge area, West Balkan Mts, Western Bulgaria).

Bulgarian–Serbian state border and the Iskar River Gorge. These outliers rise above a broad denudation plane, which is developed onto a large slab of diverse Paleozoic and Triassic rocks. Amongst them, the most prominent is that of the Zimevitsa Plateau, which is composed of thick Jurassic–Lower Cretaceous sedimentary rocks. The Zimevitsa Plateau comprises several late Alpine NW–SE trending disharmonic folds that include moderately folded lower Bajocian–Berriasian offshore argillaceous sediments and carbonate hemipelagic/pelagic rocks, following upon less deformed upper Sinemurian–Aalenian shallow-marine terrigenous-carbonate strata (Moskovski, 1997, 2001; see also Fig. 2*a, b*). These local-scale structures, described by Moskovski (2001) as “Zimevitsa Folds”, are developed above the Vidlich overthrust, a regional shearing structure, along which the Srednogorie Zone was thrust northwards over the Balkan Zone.

The Middle Jurassic in the Zimevitsa Plateau is subdivided into four lithostratigraphic units, which alternate superpositionally: Ozirovo Formation (uppermost part); Etropole Formation; Bov Formation; and Yavorets Formation (lowermost part). The overall stratigraphic log of this succession was recently given by Metodiev *et al.* (2014), and only the Etropole Formation will be the subject of special attention herein. The main outcrops of the formation are on the western slopes of the Zimevitsa Plateau, in particular in the cores of the anticlines that make it up, which are exposed by extensive landslides (Fig. 2*a, b*). This especially applies to the Dobravitsa anticline and its adjacent folds, which are well visible in the eastern vicin-

ity of the eponymous village. To the southwest, the rocks of Etropole Formation are downthrown along the valley of the Brezenska River and crop out in a few isolated sites around Breze Village (Fig. 3*a*). In this area, the Etropole Formation and the overlying Jurassic rocks are intensively deformed due to the close proximity of the Vidlich overthrust. Relatively good exposures exist near the summit of Mogilata (Fig. 3*b*). In this areal extent, the Etropole Formation encompasses a narrow strip-like NE–SW trending outcrop record with a length of a few kilometers. According to Metodiev *et al.* (2014), the thickness of the formation is ~90 m, with a total chronostratigraphic extent from the uppermost part of the Aalenian to the upper part of the lower Bajocian.

The bulk of the Etropole Formation in the area of the Zimevitsa Plateau is composed of dark gray to rusty-brown, non-calcareous to slightly calcareous, silty shales that are thin-bedded, generally fissile, and typically with a fine parallel lamination. Concretions are very abundant and show a wide variety of shapes, sizes and composition. Lower shale levels usually contain randomly spaced (both in clusters and segregations) concretions. Concretions are especially well developed in the middle and the upper parts of the Etropole Formation, where they may occur in parallel rows distributed along definite horizons. The latter refer particularly to the outcrops in the Dobravitsa anticline, in which at least 45 distinct concretary horizons were observed. According to their mineral composition, concretions are made of sphaeroiderite, calcite (often pyrite-bearing), phosphorite and pyrite. The rocks of the Etropole Formation also contain unevenly dis-

Fig. 2. Location and aerial photograph of the main area of this study: *a*) geological map of the Zimevitsa Plateau (modified from Moskovski, 2001) with sketch of the fold structures; *b*) panoramic view of the Zimevitsa Plateau from the west, representing the main structures among the “Zimevitsa Folds” (the synclines are marked with squares and the anticlines are indicated with circles); 1 – Prepasnitsa syncline; 2 – Dobravitsa anticline; 3 – Lokven syncline; 4 – Sarbenitsa anticline (photo: Oleg Vasilev); the location of the type section for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etopole Formation is shown both here and on the map with orange arrows; note the black shales comprising the core of the Dobravitsa anticline and the thick Middle Jurassic–Lower Cretaceous carbonates composing its limbs and those of the adjacent folds.

Fig. 3. Location and general view of the Brezenska River Valley: *a*) geological map of the area southwest of Breze Village, including the auxiliary reference section for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etopole Formation (orange arrow); *b*) panoramic view of the right slope of the Brezenska River Valley from the southeast; note intense deformations of the Jurassic rocks due to their close proximity to the Vidlich overthrust.

tributed fossils, mainly ammonites and belemnites. The fossil-bearing levels are assigned to the lower and especially the upper parts of the formation. Summary data on the fossil ranges were given by Metodiev *et al.* (2014).

A 10-m to 20-m thick wedge-shaped body of alternating shales, siltstones and fine-grained sandstones is interbedded in the middle part of the Etopole Formation. The best and fully exposed development of this body was localized in the core of the Dobravitsa

anticline, in close proximity to Dobravitsa Village. A few more outcrops of it were also observed in the area surrounding this village, as well as near Breze Village. Moderately exposed and less thick development of this body was also localized to the southwest of Breze Village. Westwards and eastwards of this area of distribution, these specific lithologies do not occur and, presumably, pass laterally into shales of the Etopole Formation. Hence, the geographic extent of this lithologic body is a few square kilometers.

It displays, however, sufficient continuity and stable properties to be established as a formal lithostratigraphic unit of lower rank in the Etropole Formation. Therefore, the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation is defined herein, and its best developments are designated as stratotype and auxiliary reference sections for the new member.

**DOBRAVITSA MEMBER OF THE ETROPOLE FORMATION (NEW MEMBER)
ДОБРАВИШКИ ЧЛЕН НА ЕТРОПОЛСКАТА СВИТА (НОВ ЧЛЕН)**

The stratigraphy of the complete succession, from the base of the Aalenian to the base of the Callovian, can be found in the paper of Metodiev *et al.* (2014). The following is a summary of the upper and lower parts of the successions, with emphasis on the lithologies defining the new member. Closer field views figured in this study are listed in the detailed stratigraphic sections that follow (see Figs 4–6).

Nomenclature

The member is named after Dobravitsa Village (Sofia District), located at the western slope of the Zimevitsa Plateau (Western Balkan Mts, West Bulgaria). The holostatotype designated herein is a section in the Dobravitsa anticline, 0.5 km east of Dobravitsa Village (N 43°01'36.84"; E 23°15'4.65") (see Figs 2, 4). Auxiliary reference section is a composite section 1.5 km southwest of Breze Village (N 43°0'59.44"; E 23°12'16.97") (see Figs 3, 4).

Lithology/Definition

The new member comprises an irregular alternation of dark gray silty shales, rusty-brown siltstones and fine-grained sandstones. Sphaeroidite and calcite concretions are distributed along definite horizons. It is distinguished from the surrounding shales of the Etropole Formation by the abundance of coarser siliciclastic lithologies.

Description of the holostatotype

Cover

Bov Formation (lower part, 3.30 m; lower Bajocian; *Stephanoceras humphriesianum* Zone and Subzone). Gray silty marlstones with internal planar stratification or laminated bedding, grading rapidly towards the base into dark gray silty shales. Three concretionary horizons containing small phosphorite nodules occur at the very base, middle and upper part. Scattered, strongly altered (oxidized) pyrite concretions also occur. Huge belemnite rostra of the genus *Megateuthis* and smaller rostra of *Belemnopsis* are found throughout. Several ammonites, defined as *Pseudoteloceras maerteni* Pavia & Fernández-Lopez, *Chondroceras evolvenscens* (Waagen) and *Nannina* ex gr. *evoluta* Buckman, are also found.

Holostatotype

Pack No. (Thickness)

14. (~50 m). Etropole Formation, upper part (lower Bajocian; *Stephanoceras humphriesianum* Zone, *Dorsetensia romani* Subzone–*Otoites sauzei* Zone). Silty shales, non-calcareous, dark gray to black, with laminated bedding. Sharp shale-on-shale contacts, dividing levels with different degree of fissility or siltiness are present. A steep décollement boundary separates the upper (slightly deformed, ~15 m thick) parts and those (moderately folded) below. Long parallel rows of concretions distributed in 35 horizons, in 1.5–2 m, occur. Concretions are large and weather on the shale surface, either subspheroidal or flattened and elongated along the stratification, and are composed of both pyrite-bearing calcite and siderite. Siderite concretions are predominant. Uppermost levels include randomly distributed phosphorite nodules, often containing ammonites. Large reticulated pyrite lumps and pyritized wood fragments occur in certain levels. The uppermost levels of the Etropole Formation (12-m thick strata, above the décollement boundary) yield an ammonite succession, which is dominated by two species identified from numerous specimens: *Dorsetensia romani*

Fig. 4. Lithologic logs of the holostatotype (a) and the auxiliary reference section (b) for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation. Key for lithology and textural elements: 1 – micritic limestone; 2 – recrystallized limestone; 3 – marlstone; 4 – shale; 5 – siltstone; 6 – sandstone; 7 – sandy siltstone; 8 – ferruginous crust; 9 – phosphate-bearing lense; 10 – siderite concretion; 11 – calcite concretion; 12 – pyrite concretion; 13 – phosphate concretion; 14 – planar lamination (high fissility); 15 – planar poor lamination (low fissility); 16 – wavy parallel lamination; 17 – massive structure; 18 – bioturbation; 19 – deformed bed; 20 – fault.

Fig. 5. Macroscopic characteristics of the rocks composing the holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation (for the stratigraphic positions of the captured intervals, see Fig. 4): *a, b*) field views of the strata from the very base of the Dobravitsa Member (pack Nos. 2–5) representing shale-sandstone couplets, which are thinning and fining upwards; *c*) fine-grained structureless sandstones with interbedded laminated shales (pack No. 2); *d*) sandstone bed surrounding large, slightly flattened, concentrically zoned siderite concretions (pack No. 2); *e*) slightly rough upper bedding plane of a sandstone bed (pack No. 2); *f*) the very base of a bedset of siltstones with slightly wavy lamination underlain by fissile shales (pack No. 9); *g*) micaceous shales with different degree of fissility and siltiness, intercalated with thin-bedded sandstones (pack No. 8); *h*) another segment of the same pack as the previous example, showing a large concentrically zoned siderite concretion in shales capped by thin sandstone bed; *i*) fissile shales, interbedded with thin siltstone layers with sharp bounding planes and nearly flat lamination (pack No. 12); *j*) medium-sized concentrically zoned siderite concretions with wide interior nodules and thin external cores, in laminated shales (pack No. 12); *k*) composite bedset of thin-bedded siltstones with planar internal stratification and interbedded silty shales with poorly laminated bedding (pack No. 13); *l*) composite bedset of thin-bedded siltstones and interbedded silty shales, with gradational contacts and fine, slightly wavy lamination (pack No. 10); *m*) thin-bedded shale-siltstone alternation (pack No. 8); *n*) large platter-shaped concretion with two interior nodules, overlying slightly folded siltstone layer within fissile shales; note that both the rocks and concretion have cleavage and segmentation (pack No. 14).

- (Opel) and *D. complanata* Buckman. Other less common forms of *Dorsetensia* are also recorded. Belemnites of the genera *Belemnopsis* and *Brachybelus* are found as well. Below the décollement boundary, fossils are rare, of the same belemnite genera, but also ammonites defined as *Stephanoceras scalare* (Weisert), *Skirroceras nodosum* (Quenstedt), *Bradfordia (Iokastelia) costidensa* Imlay, *B. (I.) praeradiata* (Douvillé), *Nannina delatfalcata* (Quenstedt), *Witchellia jugifera* (Waagen), *Oxyerites* spp. and *Otoites* spp., occur as isolated specimens in some levels.
- 13–2. (21.5 m). Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation (lower Bajocian, *Witchellia laeviuscula* Zone, *pars.*)
13. (0.60 m). A composite bedset of thin-bedded, rusty-brown, ferruginized siltstones and interbedded gray, thin-bedded, silty shales. Siltstones display planar internal stratification, whereas shales are poorly laminated.
12. (2.30 m). Shales, gray, fissile, silty and non-calcareous, thin- to medium-bedded, alternating with thin-bedded, ferruginized rusty-brown siltstones. Siltstones may have both sharp and indistinct bounding planes and nearly flat to slightly wavy fine lamination. Four horizons of medium-sized subspheroidal siderite concretions are observed.
11. (1.50 m). Shales, dark gray, non-calcareous, laminated, fissile. A row of siderite concretions and one more of large calcite concretions occur at upper part. Both shales and concretions are moderately deformed in small-scale folds, fractures and calcite fillings.
10. (0.80 m). A composite bedset of thin-bedded, ferruginized rusty-brown siltstones and interbedded dark gray silty shales with gradational contacts. Both siltstones and shales have slightly wavy lamination, in which individual coarse silt laminae range in thickness to a few millimeters.
9. (1.30 m). Two bedsets of pale-brown to beige, thin-bedded, ferruginized siltstones with fine slightly wavy lamination. The upper bedset contains large and flattened siderite concretions, which are elongated parallel to the stratification.
8. (5.60 m). Shales, dark gray, non-calcareous, horizontally laminated, with different degrees of fissility and siltiness, and irregularly intercalated very thin layers of very fine-grained, slightly calcareous, ferruginized rusty-brown quartz sandstones. Shales are abundant in mica flakes. Five horizons of medium-sized subspheroidal to flattened siderite concretions are observed.
7. (1.60 m). The same shales and sandstones as above, but sandstones are thin-bedded and more common, with planar internal stratification and sharp bounding planes. Shales are moderately bioturbated. A concretionary horizon of large calcite concretions is seen in the shales.
6. (1.80 m). Shales, dark gray, non-calcareous, laminated and fissile, interbedded with thin layers of massive, ferruginized rusty-brown fine-grained sandstones. A sandstone bed of a mid-level contains large flattened siderite concretions.
5. (0.70 m). Alternation of thin-bedded, fine-grained, ferruginized rusty-brown sandstones and gray shales.
4. (0.50 m). Shales, gray, non-calcareous, laminated, bounded by thin-bedded, fine-grained, rusty-brown ferruginized sandstones. Shales contain large spheroidal calcite concretions, as well as small oxidized pyrite nodules. They are irregularly stained by fine-grained pyrite masses, on which intense weathering has produced yellowish sulfurous patina. Fragmentary pyritized molds of large *Riccardiceras* spp. are found.

Fig. 6. Macroscopic characteristics of the rocks from the auxiliary reference section for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation (for the stratigraphic positions of the captured intervals, see Fig. 4): *a*) the boundary interval between the Yavorets and Bov formations (pack Nos. 8, 9); the hammer is placed on deformed laminated marlstones of the Bov Formation; *b*) uneven bedding plane with lenses containing abraded phosphate pebbles within micritic limestones from the base of the Yavorets Formation (pack No. 9); *c*) fissile laminated shales from the upper part of the Etropole Formation (pack No. 6); *d, e*) silty shales with concentrically zoned siderite concretion (*ibid.*, pack No. 5); *f*) silty shales containing thin lens-like ferruginized silty layers and scattered siderite concretions (*ibid.*, pack No. 4); *g*) thin-bedded, ferruginized sandy siltstones alternating with fissile shales from the uppermost part of the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation (pack No. 3); *h*) ferruginized sandy siltstones interbedded with fissile shales (*ibid.*, pack No. 2).

3. (1.20 m). Shales, gray, non-calcareous, laminated, enclosing two rows of subspheroidal siderite concretions.
2. (3.30 m). Alternation of thin-bedded, rusty-brown, fine-grained, slightly calcareous ferruginized sandstones and gray laminated shales. Sandstones are structureless and often surround large flattened siderite concretions. Shales are moderately bioturbated by *Teichichnus* at certain levels. This part of the succession displays sharply defined bounding surfaces.
1. (~3 m). Etropole Formation (uppermost lower part). Shales, dark gray, non-calcareous, fissile. Rare and unevenly distributed siderite concretions occur. A few fragmentary ammonite specimens of *Euhoplloceras* spp. and belemnite rostra of *Belemnopsis* are found.

Underlying strata

Etropole Formation (lower part, ~20 m; lower Bajocian; *Witchellia laeviuscula* Zone–*Hyperlioceras discites* Zone). Shales, non-calcareous, dark gray to gray-brown, laminated and fissile. Scattered siderite concretions and clayey-phosphorite nodules occur. The ammonite record includes scattered and fragmentary graphoceratids, oppeliids and hammatoceratids. Belemnite rostra of the genera *Belemnopsis*, *Holcobelus* and *Brachybelus* are relatively common.

Description of the auxiliary reference section

Pack No. (Thickness)

9. (0.50 m). Yavorets Formation, basal part, middle Callovian (lowermost part)–lower Callovian (*Hecticoceras* spp. Zone (*pars.*)–*Macrocephalites gracilis* Zone (*pars.*)). Limestones, light gray, medium-bedded, micritic, bounded at the base by thin red-brown ferriferous crust, which has inconsistent thickness and sharp contacts. It corresponds to two beds separated by uneven bedding plane,

- on which thin pinching lenses with abundant abraded phosphatic pebbles are developed. The latter represent reworked nodules that often include reworked lower Bajocian ammonites of the genus *Dorsetensia*: *D. romani* (Opel); *D. edouardiana* (d'Orbigny); and *Dorsetensia* ex gr. *liostraca* Buckman. The phosphorite-bearing level lies on a sharp bioeroded and encrusted surface, which hosts phosphatized nuclei of small *Argutostrea* bivalves and serpulid tubes. In the matrix of the phosphorite-bearing level, poorly preserved ammonites of *Eulunulites* ex gr. *lunula* (Reinecke) occur, while, above it, rare *Rossienceras* spp. are found.
- 8–7. (3.50 m). Bov Formation (? upper Bathonian (*pars.*)).
8. (0.70 m). Marlstones, gray-brown, laminated, deformed. Cemented fractures (mineralized and sealed by dark calcite and clay minerals) are common. Deformation bands are also seen as networks of light lines with narrow apertures. Rubble zones, tens of centimeters thick, are commonly developed on the underlying rocks. No fossils are found.
7. (2.80 m). Limestones, gray, yellowish when altered, thin-bedded, recrystallized, bounded at the top by an inconsistent gray argillaceous layer. These rocks are truncated at the top by a fault and the upper parts are intensely tectonized. The first few centimeters at the very base are heavily bioturbated, and the bioturbation comprises dense branching burrows of *Chondrites*. Small indefinable fragments of belemnites are present throughout.
- 6–4. (9.00 m). Etropole Formation (upper part).
6. (2.50 m). Shales, dark gray, non-calcareous, fissile, with fine laminated bedding. A concretionary horizon of large calcite concretions occurs at the top.
5. (1.50 m). The same shales as above, but the rocks are lighter in color and with increased siltiness, forming a distinct bank. At a few decimeter-thick levels with diffused contacts, shales become silty and include siderite concretions. Calcite concretions also occur, though rarely. Poorly preserved *Emileia* sp. indet. was found.

4. (5.00 m). Similar shales as above, but darker in color and less fissile. Centimeter-thick lens-like ferruginized silty layers with small siderite concretions occur.
- 3–2. (10.20 m). Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation.
3. (2.00 m). Shales, non-calcareous, dark gray, thin-bedded, fissile. Thin beds of ferruginized sandy siltstones are developed within the shales, especially in the higher levels.
2. (8.20 m). Shales, non-calcareous, dark gray to black, with laminated bedding. Sharp, shale-on-shale contacts, separating levels with different fissility and siltiness are present. Thin beds (<10 cm thick) of ferruginized sandy siltstones occur interbedded with the shales. Three concretionary horizons of large calcite concretions occur at the top, at the base and in the middle.
1. (~4.50 m). Etropole Formation, lower part (lower Bajocian). Shales, non-calcareous, dark gray to black, laminated. The strata host at least two deformed horizons, in which faulted beds, small-scale folds, fractures and mineral fillings, as well as smooth cleavage surfaces with fine-grained powder coatings, are developed. Strongly flattened or pinched siderite concretions occur. Deformed horizons are bound above by undeformed shale beds with horizontal bedding plane surfaces.

Underlying strata

Etropole Formation (lowermost part, unknown total thickness; presumably lower Bajocian). Shales, non-calcareous, dark gray to gray-brown, laminated to poorly laminated. Exposure is too poor to trace the strata either vertically or in superposition. Randomly distributed siderite concretions and clayey-phosphorite nodules were seen in a few isolated levels. Fossils are rare and consist of belemnite rostra of the genera *Belemnopsis* and *Holcobelus*.

Biostratigraphic data

All beds of the uppermost part of the Etropole Formation, exposed above the décollement boundary at the core of the Dobravitsa anticline, belong to the *Stephanoceras humphriesianum* Zone. The same holds true for the overlying strata from the lower part of the Bov Formation. Collectively, these sediments, and a few more adjacent outcrops of the Zimevitsa Plateau, yielded characteristic specimens of the genera *Pseudoteloceras* and *Chondroceras*, as well as a continuous succession of ammonites of the genus *Dorsetensia*, which are indicative of the lowermost part of the *Stephanoceras humphriesianum* and *Dorsetensia romani* subzones. This is the most expanded ammonite sequence ever recorded in the lower Bajocian in Bulgaria, and certainly includes good local equivalents of the respective ammonite

subzones in NW Europe (see Dietze *et al.*, 2008, 2011, 2015; see also Pavia and Fernandez-Lopez, 2016). As stated above, below the décollement boundary, observed in the same site, ammonites are less common, but the recorded specimens of *Stephanoceras*, *Skirroceras*, *Nannina*, *Bradfordia* (*Iokastelia*) and *Otoites* indicate both the lower part of the lower Bajocian *Stephanoceras humphriesianum* Zone and the *Otoites sauzei* Zone (*ibid.*), the latter with a still unspecified extent and boundaries in the section. The ammonite rarities from the beds of the holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation do not allow precise biostratigraphic alignment. However, in the presence of *Witchellia*, *Riccardiceras* and *Euhoplaceras*, it can be suggested that these rocks belong to an indefinite (probably lower) part of the *Witchellia laeviuscula* Zone of the lower Bajocian, which in Bulgaria is applied with a wider scope than elsewhere (see Dietze *et al.*, 2001, 2007).

The auxiliary reference section for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation is a nice example showing structural and lithological indicators for a local stratigraphic discontinuity at the overlying strata of the Etropole Formation. The finds of diagnostic allochthonous Callovian ammonites at the very base of the Yavorets Formation, which are mixed with reburied lower Bajocian ammonites of *Dorsetensia*, is a clear evidence for a long-term non-deposition spanning from the mid-early Bajocian to the beginning of the early Callovian. On the other hand, the Callovian examples of *Eulunulites* and *Rossienceras* are evidence for a limited presence of the lowermost middle Callovian (*Hecticoceras* spp. Zone) and the mid-lower Callovian (*Macrocephalites gracilis* Zone), zonal names with Bulgarian usage, but equivalent to coeval zones from NW Europe (see Elmi, 1967; Thierry *et al.*, 1997). The beds referred to the Bov Formation probably represent an imbricated part of the succession, which, by analogy with closely located ammonite-bearing strata with similar lithology, is conditionally assigned to the upper Bathonian. The only find of *Emileia* sp. indet. from the shales of the Etropole Formation above the Dobravitsa Member suggests that these levels belong to the *Witchellia laeviuscula* Zone. Taking into account the overall stratigraphic occurrence of the ammonite genus *Emileia*, from well-recorded European successions (*e.g.*, Dietze *et al.*, 2007), it can be assumed that, at this site, the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation may belong to the lowermost part of the *Witchellia laeviuscula* Zone.

Regional aspects

As noted above, the rocks of Etropole Formation have a broad (regional-scale) development in Bulgaria. According to the data from earlier Bulgarian literature, the distribution of the Etropole Formation is

confined to two main subsiding areas, presently having exposures in the Godech and Etropole–Teteven regions (West Balkan–Central Fore-Balkan Mts), but mainly with an extensive subsurface occurrence in the Montana–Pleven region (Moesia) (Fig. 7). Owing to the previous careful field studies and the

Fig. 7. Map of the lateral distribution (a) and selected field views representing the lithologies of the Etropole Formation and some coeval lateral lithological equivalents (b–h): a) subcrop and outcrop occurrence of the Etropole Formation and its lateral lithological equivalents on the tectonic sketch-map of Bulgaria (compiled according to data from Sapunov *et al.*, 1985a, b; 1986a, b; 1988; 1991; 1994; 1996; 1999); b) laminated, dark gray shales containing a horizon of siderite concretions and lenticular siderite layers from the holostratotype for the Etropole Formation near the town of Etropole (Sofia District), lower Bajocian, *W. laeviuscula* Zone; c) interbedded siderite layers and lines of siderite concretions in fissile black shales of the Stefanets Member of the Etropole Formation (locality south of Lopyan Village, Sofia District), lower Bajocian, *W. laeviuscula* Zone; d) shale-siltstone alternation from the middle part of the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation (holostratotype, No. 8, lower Bajocian, *W. laeviuscula* Zone; see Fig. 4); e) upper bed plain of dark gray, argillaceous siltstones with altered siderite concretions of the Nefela Member of the Etropole Formation (locality near Gorno Ozirovo Village, Montana District), lower Bajocian, probably *S. humphriesianum* Zone; f) laminated, thin-bedded argillaceous siltstones with flaser bedding from the type-section for the Shipkovo Member of the Etropole Formation (locality near Shipkovo Village, Lovech District), lower Bajocian; g) thin- to medium-bedded, fine-grained sandstones of the Lopyan Member of the Etropole Formation (locality south of Ribaritsa Village, Lovech District), lower Bajocian; h) core photograph showing well-sorted, fine-grained sandstone and siltstone layers with sharp upper contacts and internal ripple cross-laminae (light gray), interbedded with shale layers (dark gray) of the Esenitsa Formation (borehole section R-1 Zlatitsa, depth 2380 m; location near Dolna Zlatitsa Village, Targovishte District), lower Bajocian.

Key for the tectonic zones (1–5) and for the areal extent of the Etropole Formation and its equivalents (6–11): 1 – Moesian Platform; 2 – South Carpathian orogen; 3 – Balkan Zone; 4 – Srednogorie Zone; 5 – Morava Zone; 6 – Etropole Formation (undivided); 7 – Etropole Formation including the Dobravitsa Member; 8 – Etropole Formation divided into Stefanets and Nefela members; 9 – Etropole Formation divided into Stefanets, Lopyan and Shipkovo members; 10 – Esenitsa Formation; 11 – shallow-water lithological equivalents (Ozirovo, Kichera and Gradets formations) or areas of non-deposition.

good borehole control, both the vertical and lateral distribution of the lithologies composing the Etropole Formation have been well defined to date. The extent of mudrocks in the Etropole Formation presumably follows paleotopographic lows, where the terrigenous input was at a minimum. This applies to the areas, in which the Etropole Formation either is homogeneous or its lower part comprises the Stefanets Member, in particular in its type-area around Etropole (Fig. 7a–c), but also in many localities of the West Balkan and Central Fore-Balkan Mts and Moesia. The silt- and sand-rich lithologic bodies amongst the strata of the Etropole Formation may be more or less local in scope, as in the case of the Dobravitsa and Nefela members (Fig. 7a, d, e), but also with a sub-regional extent, such as the Shipkovo Member and especially the Lopyan Member (see Fig. 7a, f, g). All these correspond to levels and areas with increased terrigenous influx. The Dobravitsa Member has the most limited distribution, forming a moderately thick wedge-shaped stratum, which is restricted only to the Godech area. The Nefela Member is confined mainly to subsurface occurrences, middling in thickness, and less to isolated exposures in the Montana region. It is delineable in boreholes but is less confineable in outcrops. Almost the same holds true for the developments of the Shipkovo Member, which displays a

spotted occurrence in the Etropole–Teteven region and to the northeast of it. The Lopyan Member is a thick, northward-thinning and narrowing wedge, stretching from the Etropole–Teteven to the Pleven region and beyond it to the northwest. Eastwards from the Pleven region, in the subsurface fields of NE Bulgaria, the rocks of the Etropole Formation grade laterally into those of the Esenitsa Formation (see Fig. 7a, h). Both formations are often confused with each other as the Esenitsa Formation has been mostly evidenced by drilling data. Nevertheless, the Etropole Formation and the Esenitsa Formation are distinctly different in terms of both lithology and fossil contents.

NOTES ON THE CONCRETIONS OF THE ETROPOLE FORMATION

Albeit diagenetic in origin, siderite concretions in the sediments of the Etropole Formation have been deemed to be a diagnostic element of the unit since its introduction (see Sapunov, 1969). Indeed, these rocks are very often heavily grounded and only the weathered siderite concretions imply the presence of the unit on the field. The pioneering, and so far only, exhaustive study of siderite concretions from

Fig. 8. Photographs and axial sections of representative concretions from the Etropole Formation (white bar = 1 cm): a) vertical section of concentrically zoned infolded siderite concretion, with black incomplete and partly phosphatized interior nodule (in) and gray external core (ec), containing pyritized wood fragment (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 14); b) altered surface of the same sample (note the unclear internal structure of the sample of such surface); c) vertical section of concentrically zoned siderite concretion with well-preserved black interior nodule and gray external core, divided by thin transient layer (tl) containing micrograined sulphides; the sample also shows fractures dissimilar to bedding filled with Fe-calcite (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 14); d) altered surface of the same sample as c (note that both the interior nodule and the external core weathered differently, and thus the internal zoning is clearly distinguishable); e) vertical section of heavily cracked rinded siderite concretion; the abundant parallel-sided Fe-calcite veins with rough margins are approximately conformable to the cleavage of, and extend from, the host shales (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 11); f) horizontal section of concentrically zoned pyritiferous siderite concretion with radial crack infillings (white arrows) and dotted concentric pyritization (white asterisks) (from the lower part of the Etropole Fm., locality Zasele, Zimevitsa Plateau); g) horizontal section of a septarian siderite concretion with lenticular and parallel-sided septarian cracks filled with calcite microspar (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 12); h) vertical section of a septarian siderite concretion consisting of well-developed, cloudy-white-calcite-filled septaria (spt) with a few sphalerite (Sph) angular grains in black fine-grained nodule matrix (brecciated in the middle), and veinlets of Fe-calcite (from the Stefanets Mb. of the Etropole Fm., locality Gradezhnitsa); i) horizontal section of a concretion composed of dark gray calcite matrix having larger, irregularly-shaped blocky pyrite (Py) domains in the center and smaller oval ones in the outer parts (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 14); j) vertical section of calcite concretion similar to the previous sample, but having pyrite infillings developed in shrinkage cracks and caverns (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 4); k) vertical section of concentrically zoned goethite-hematite concretion with strongly altered loose inner void and oxidized, thin-banded, external core with porous-cavernous structure (holostratotype for the Stefanets Mb. of the Etropole Fm., locality Glozhene); l) the same type of concretion as the previous sample, but having well-preserved black interior nodule and fresh, thin-banded, external core (Stefanets Mb. of the Etropole Fm., locality Gradezhnitsa); m) bumped inner surface of broken goethite concretion (holostratotype for the Stefanets Mb. of the Etropole Fm., locality Glozhene); n) iron-oxide-cemented rods protruding from the inner surface of broken goethite concretion (*ibid.*); o) irregularly-shaped concretion with narrow hollow interior and thick external core made of very fine-grained goethite (*ibid.*).

the Etropole Formation (Atanasov, 1959) revealed that the concretions are both septarian (with calcite-sphalerite-barite-filled septaria) and concentrically zoned. It was also evidenced that the bulk of them consist of interior nodules of increased volumetric

siderite (80–86 mol% FeCO_3) and external coats of more impure siderite (50–68 mol% FeCO_3) with significant clay-silt admixtures (*ibid.*). In addition, according to the structural evidence, the concretions were everywhere seen to be normal to the surround-

ing bedding, thus indicating that they have formed prior to the maximum burial depths attained by the host rocks. From these data, it can be inferred that the siderite concretions were generally formed in rapidly accumulating sediments associated with marine depositional environments (cf. Gauthier, 1982; Mozley, 1989).

A few examples of siderite concretions from both the holostatotype and the auxiliary reference section for the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation have already been illustrated herein (see Figs 5, 6). The following lines include a few more samples from these sections, as well as several other samples from two more localities of the Etropole Formation from outside the area of the Zimevitsa Plateau. In brief, the focus herein is put on: 1) concentrically zoned siderite concretions; 2) septarian siderite concretions; 3) calcite concretions; and 4) iron oxyhydroxide concretions (see Fig. 8). More data on these and other examples will be given elsewhere.

Concentrically zoned siderite concretions

The concentrically zoned siderite concretions are the most common type in the rocks of the Etropole Formation from the Zimevitsa Plateau area. Both the earlier and our record revealed that this type of concretions may occur throughout the whole extent of the unit, and this also includes the Dobravitsa Member. No systematic variations in either the stratigraphical distribution or host rock preference have been observed. These concretions typically range in diameter from 10 cm to 20 cm, but locally are as small as 2 cm and as large as 30–40 cm. The concretions, composing parallel rows in horizons, are usually of similar shape and size. Their margins

are rounded, and most are ellipsoidal to spherical, sometimes weakly lobate or discoidal. They typically comprise massive interior nodules and external cores (Fig. 8a–d), usually divided by millimeter-thick transient layers that commonly contain micrograined sulphides, usually pyrite (Fig. 9a–c), but often also chalcocopyrite. Large, platter-shaped concretions with two or more interior nodules, probably formed by the coalescence of adjacent concretions, are also present. Frequently, this type of concretions may comprise ringed examples, having massive interior nodules and very thin external cores (Fig. 8e). Concretion interiors and external cores have a similar mineralogical composition and differ in the amounts of the main minerals and admixtures. The interiors and cores mainly consist of siderite and Mg-calcite, but may also contain kaolinite, hematite and dolomite. These comprise brown micrite matrix (80–85%) and allochems (Fig. 9d–f). The latter may include sparse sponge spicules, reworked bivalve bioclasts, unclear recrystallized bioclasts and filaments, as well as sporadic radiolarians and foraminifera. Clastic grains, such as quartz silt, feldspars and muscovite, may also be present in small amounts.

The concentrically zoned siderite concretions are often pyritiferous. Pyrite may occur as loose-radial to dense-reticulate aggregates that partially or almost completely replace the concretion interior (e.g., Fig. 8f). It also may seldom occur as scattered crystal euhedron clusters or replacing fossils. Atanasov (1959) exclusively thought the pyritization of the siderite concretions as linked with post-sedimentary magmatic activity, affecting the rocks of the Etropole Formation, and gave examples from many Bulgarian deposits. Since no signs of magmatic activity in the Zimevitsa Plateau area have

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Fig. 9. Backscattered electron (BSE) images (a–c) and thin-section photomicrographs (d–i) of the interior nodules of siderite concretions (photographs courtesy of G. Lütov and M. Georgieva): a–c) sections of a nodule of concentrically zoned concretion comprising very fine-grained siderite (Sd) to clayey-siderite (cl-Sd) matrix, patchy calcite (Ca) and ferroan calcite (Fe-Ca) cement, scattered quartz (Q), apatite (Ap) and chlorite (Chl) grains, phosphatized (Ap; Ca-Ap) lumps, as well as euhedral microcrysts and oxidized aggregates of pyrite (Py) (Etropole Fm., from the same level as the sample in Fig. 8c, d); d–f) sections of a nodule of concentrically zoned concretion (Etropole Fm., a few meters below the sample in Fig. 8c, d); d – micrite intraclast (MI) among slightly recrystallized micrite matrix to microspar, containing abundant clastic components, mainly subrounded quartz grains (Q) (XPL), e – recrystallized bioclast (RB), bivalve bioclasts (BB), fragment of thin-shelled bivalve (filament, F), benthic foraminifera (BF) and subrounded quartz grains (Q) in micrite matrix (PPL), f – pyrite (Py) crystals and masses partially replacing the micrite matrix, scattered quartz grains (Q) and single muscovite flakes (Ms) are also visible (XPL); g–i) details of the septarian concretion in Fig. 8d: g – micrite matrix containing scattered subrounded quartz grains (Q) (XPL), h – internal part of septaria filled with calcite mosaic (Ca) (XPL), i – outer part of septaria with calcite crystals (Ca) containing fibrous and bladed chlorite (Chl) (XPL).

been recorded so far, the source of pyritization in this particular place should be sought elsewhere. For instance, according to some classical models (e.g., Raiswell, 1982), pyritization of carbonate concretions can occur at high levels of reactive iron and heterogeneous organic matter distribution in the host sediments. Our initial studies on the geochem-

istry of some levels containing siderite and calcite concretions indicated both high reactive iron contents and unevenly dispersed organic matter in the surrounding strata. Therefore, the pyritization of the siderite concretions from *in situ* sources, as well as of the calcite concretions described below seems possible.

Septarian siderite concretions

The septarian siderite concretions have been observed in many localities of the Etropole Formation from the Central Balkan and Fore-Balkan Mts (see Atanasov, 1959; see also Fig. 8h), but in the Zimevitsa Plateau area they seem to be less common. Only a few samples were seen in the shales surrounding the Dobravitsa Member (e.g., Fig. 8g). In terms of their size range and external morphology, these concretions are similar to the concentrically zoned ones, and the same holds true for the mineral composition (see above). The septarian concretions, however, comprise massive nodules and very thin external cores of iron oxyhydroxides. Nodules are usually composed of micrite matrix (e.g., Fig. 9g) and contain lenticular shrinkage cracks, which are broadest near the center and taper towards the concretion exterior. The cracks are filled with cloudy, white, light-gray to black calcite (septaria) (see Fig. 9h, i). Sphalerite angular grains, included in some septaria, were also observed. Our observations show that the septarian concretions are present in intervals containing concretions both with and without cracks. Therefore, their lesser presence in the rocks of the Zimevitsa Plateau area than in other coeval Bulgarian localities suggests more inappropriate conditions for crack development.

Calcite concretions

The calcite concretions have surprisingly been evidenced to be a fairly common component of the

Etropole Formation in both the holostratotype strata and those of the auxiliary section for the Dobravitsa Member. They compose separate concretionary horizons and are less commonly scattered within the shale beds. Calcite concretions usually range in diameter from 10 cm to 20 cm and rarely reach larger size. Their margins are rounded, with a rough surface. Most are ovoid, but often display teardrop shape, with protruding pitted upper end and rounded bottom. They usually comprise an interior composed of Mg-calcite with irregular patches of siderite, which includes as textural forms brown micrite matrix, a moderate amount of detrital silt to very fine sand-sized quartz, scattered feldspars, muscovite flakes, poor set of stable accessory minerals, as well as scarce sponge spicules, bivalve detritus and benthic foraminifera (Fig. 10a–i). Calcite concretions are often pyritiferous, containing crack infillings of blocky pyrite, finely disseminated micro-pyrite masses, irregularly shaped pyritization zones of granular pyrite or millimeter-scale pyrite-bearing caverns (see Fig. 8i, j).

Iron oxyhydroxide concretions

Although this type of concretions is not typical for the area of the Zimevitsa Plateau, it is noted herein as being a curious issue that requires consideration. The iron oxyhydroxide concretions were recorded in strata adjacent to levels containing both the concentrically zoned and septarian siderite concretions. The material taken into account came from two localities of the Etropole Formation: 1) Glozhene (N 42°58'54.22"; E 24°11'4.40"); and

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Fig. 10. Thin-section photomicrographs of calcite concretions (photographs courtesy of M. Georgieva): a) micrite matrix with a wood fragment (WF) and subangular clastic grains, mainly of quartz (Q) (PPL) (auxiliary reference section for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 5); b) completely recrystallized bioclast (RB) with pyritized periphery in micrite matrix (XPL) (*ibid.*); c) micrite matrix containing clastic components, predominantly quartz grains (Q), but also muscovite flakes (Ms), as well as a calcitized siliceous sponge spicule (SS) and altered crinoid bioclasts (CB) with partial pyrite filling, tighter to looser pyrite (Py) aggregates also occur (PPL) (*ibid.*); d) altered benthic foraminifer (BF) with chambers partially filled with pyrite in micrite matrix with abundant subangular clastic grains, mainly of quartz (Q) (XPL) (*ibid.*); e) slightly pyritized bivalve bioclast (BB) in micrite matrix with clastic grains (XPL) (auxiliary reference section for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 3); f) micrite matrix with common clastic grains, mainly quartz (Q), but also sporadic muscovite flakes (Ms) and a rounded zircon grain (Zr) (XPL) (*ibid.*); g) micritic matrix containing common clastic grains (mainly quartz, Q), a calcitized and partially pyritized siliceous sponge spicule (SS) is in the center (PPL) (holostratotype for the Dobravitsa Mb. of the Etropole Fm., No. 14); h) micrite intraclast (MI) among slightly recrystallized micrite matrix to microspar, containing abundant clastic components, predominantly quartz grains (Q) (XPL) (*ibid.*); i) completely recrystallized and strongly pyritized bioclast (RB) included in micrite matrix (XPL) (*ibid.*).

2) Gradezhnitsa (N 43°00'40.29"; E 24°14'22.08") (Central Fore-Balkan Mts). The former locality corresponds to the type-section for the Stefanets Member (see Sapunov and Tchoumatchenco, 1989), and the latter field takes part of a ~20-m

thick succession of the Stefanets Member of the Etropole Formation. Both localities yielded iron oxyhydroxide concretions from mid-upper levels that are presumably of the *Stephanoceras humphriesianum* Zone.

Fig. 11. Backscattered electron (BSE) images of the external cores of an iron oxyhydroxide concretion (details of the sample in Fig. 8d, photographs courtesy of G. Lütov): a, b) porous-cavernous banded rinds comprising goethite (Goe), hematite (Hem) and Mn-rich ferroan calcite (Cal), quartz grains (Q) and mica flakes (M) also occur; c, d) microcaverns with colloform, reniform to platy masses of goethite (Goe) surrounded by hematite (Hem).

The iron oxyhydroxide concretions are abundant in several horizons of ferruginous fissile shales with fine laminated bedding. The concretions range from spheroids less than 1 cm in diameter to ovoids or spindle shapes up to 10 cm long and 5 cm across (Fig. 8k, l), but irregular shapes of broken, bigger, concretions are also numerous (Fig. 8m–o). The interiors of ovoid and spindle-shaped concretions are altered either to hollow inner voids or massive nodules, the latter consisting of Fe-Mg siderite and Mg-calcite. The external cores are a few centimeters thick colloform-banded rinds, with porous-cavernous structure (Fig. 11a–d), in which goethite, hematite, Mn-rich ferroan calcite and Fe-Mn oxyhydroxides alternate in millimeter-scale light and dark layers. External cores often contain subangular ferruginous lithoclasts and terrigenous grains. The irregularly shaped broken concretions display narrow hollow interiors and thick external cores that

are composed of very fine-grained goethite with minor quartz admixtures. Some are transversely septate, while others have wide central cavities, in which bumps of varying convexity and diameter are developed on inner surfaces. Iron-oxide-cemented rods, resembling coated rod furrows, were also seen as protrusions on the inner surfaces of broken concretions.

The Bulgarian material is reminiscent in many aspects to examples of iron oxyhydroxide concretions recorded from Jurassic paralic and fluvial sediments (e.g., Nejbert and Jurewicz, 2004; Loope *et al.*, 2012). A late diagenetic origin via dissolution of the siderite, from both reworked and *in situ* preserved concretions, and rapid crystallization of iron oxyhydroxides in oxygenated conditions, caused by influx of meteoric water, have been proposed. Probably, the same is true for the studied iron oxyhydroxide concretions of the Etropole Formation, but the surrounding lithology and depositional settings are quite dissimilar to the other Bulgarian and foreign examples. Therefore, more studies are needed in order to evaluate this possibility.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work is rather descriptive and many questions have arisen. Overall, the lithological characteristics of the Etropole Formation point to offshore calm water shelf environments at medium water depths. However, in connection with the statements in this paper, the mudrocks of the Etropole Formation were seen to be often intimately interbedded with sediments that do not correspond to this depositional setting, but are indicative for deposition at shallower depths under more intense hydrodynamic conditions. In addition to the previously separated members, containing coarser siliciclastic lithologies, the rocks of the Dobravitsa Member of the Etropole Formation also suggest increased influence from a nearby located coast. The latter are still poorly understood from a depositional viewpoint, but they show signs of tidal bedding, in the form of shale-sandstone to shale-siltstone couplets, which were presumably produced by alternating bottom-current and stagnant-water conditions. Therefore, apart from the typical marine deposits, sediments accumulated within a mudflat of tide-dominated estuary or bayhead delta settings may also be present. Carbonate and iron oxyhydroxide concretions from the Etropole Formation also deserve further attention as there are indications for both marine and brackish origin.

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